

DYNAMICS OF KNOWLEDGE SUPPLY TRANSACTIONS THROUGH TIME IN BULGARIAN FARMS

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Abstract

Knowledge transfer is a driving force for any business. Also, in agriculture. But there is one peculiarity. Here knowledge is individualized, i.e. related to the individual farm. This difference is caused mainly, but not only, by two reasons - a) specific natural conditions (even neighboring fields are not completely similar) and b) personal farmer's preferences (the right to choose a licensed organic production, or not, for example). The study of the economy of Bulgarian agriculture, conducted in the last two years, allowed us to discover the modes for knowledge supply used by different farmers. Moreover, this study repeated (in a more extended and advanced form) a similar one from 25 years ago, carried out by two members of the current research team. The goal of this article is to discover, analyze and explain changes in the choice of modes for knowledge supply during the past period. The research was conducted in the form of a survey and covered 345 modern Bulgarian farmers. The collected data were processed through: a) comparative quantitative analysis to detect changes over the past 25 years; b) discrete structural analysis to explain the choice of transactional mode; and c) institutional analysis to discover the causes of changes that have occurred. The main conclusion of this part of our research project is normalization. Bulgarian agricultural sector – market, private agents, and public intervention – is moving in a direction similar to those in developed countries.

Keywords: Agriculture, Governance, Knowledge Transactions.

Introduction: Knowledge as a resource

Each business is in need of various resources. Speaking about the transfer of the resources we could observe that supporting tools exist. These could be standards – in case of machinery or equipment, for example. Agricultural land is also standardized by categories. Market itself could also provide guarantees in this direction - if somebody wants to buy one unit of any currency, he or she could be sure about the value in it before the transaction. Money exchange rates exist. Sometime, reputation supports the transfer of need resources – potatoes from Samokov or apricots from Silistra and so on.

Knowledge (information, technology, advice) is also a resource in business. Its economic role is studied by many of the great economists by different perspectives: Hayek (1948) – knowledge and market, Simon (1999) - the cost of having useable knowledge, Arrow (1969) – transfer of knowledge. The transfer of knowledge differs from those of other resources. Not one of the

mechanisms, mentioned above, is available. There are no standards or the existing standards are formal. The fact that a piece of information has been useful for somebody does not guarantee the same effect for other one. Uncertainty dominates. As a result, the logic of transactions with knowledge differs from the ones of those with other resources. Oliver Williamson uses an example in which the ability to recognize the product before the transaction (supply of knowledge) defines its mode:

Institution tells us that simple governance structures should mediate simple transactions and that complex governance structures should be reserved for complex transactions. Using complex structure to govern a simple transaction incurs unneeded costs, and using simple structure to govern complex transaction invites strain. But what is simple and complex in transactional and governance respect? Technology is an obvious candidate but anomalies quickly appear. Some high-technology transactions (e.g., the procurement of semiconductors) are contractually very simple, and some low-technology transactions (e.g. the supply of molten pig iron from a blast furnace to a rolling mill) may create serious contractual hazards (Williamson 1996, p. 13).

In agriculture there is one more peculiarity. Knowledge is highly individualized, i.e. related to each individual farm. This difference is caused mainly (but not only) by two reasons: a) specific natural conditions (even neighboring fields are not completely similar) and b) personal preferences of the farmer (right to choose a licensed organic production, or not, for example). In such situation transacting with knowledge is harder, which means more expensive. A specific supporting tool is needed. Detailed view on the economic character of agrarian knowledge and related governance mechanism could be find in Bachev (2022).

Institutional economic school differs from other school in many points. One of them is that its theory is comparative by nature. It does not so much (as neoclassical school for example) interest on the analyses of one given situation itself but in comparisons to other available options. This approach is convincingly demonstrated by the newest laureates of Nobel prize in economic science. They explained “how institutions are formed and affect prosperity” (<https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/economic-sciences/2024/summary/>) comparing economic development of different countries (Acemoglu, Johnson and Robinson 2001, Acemoglu, Johnson and Robinson 2012).

Dynamic character of the theory is other major difference. That is why not simply comparisons but comparisons through time are the key to understand the nature of economic phenomena. Commenting the development policies, Douglass North, in his Nobel prize lecture, explains:

Neo-classical theory is simply an inappropriate tool to analyze and prescribe policies that will induce development. It is concerned with the operation of markets, not with how markets develop. How can one prescribe policies when one doesn't understand how economies develop? The very methods employed by neo-classical economists have dictated the subject matter and militated against such a development. That theory in the pristine form that gave it mathematical precision and elegance modeled a frictionless and static world. When applied to economic history and development it focused on technological development and more recently human capital investment, but ignored the incentive structure embodied in institutions that determined the extent of societal investment in those factors. In the analysis of economic performance

through time it contained two erroneous assumptions: one that institutions do not matter and two that time does not matter (North 1993).

Following these keystones of institutional economics, we developed our study as comparative and dynamic in our specific and relatively narrow subject.

The study: Material and method

A survey of the economy of Bulgarian agriculture was conducted in 2001. It covered 194 real functioning (not just registered) market oriented (not self-sufficient) farms. Individual, family or group type was 38%, cooperatives – 29%, business companies – 33%. Small size declared 38%, medium – 45%, large – 17%. Both structures – by type and by size, were representative for Bulgarian agriculture at that time. The details on this survey could be find in Bachev and Terziev (2001, 2002a, 2002b, 2002c, 2003a, 2003b).

During 2023-24 a new survey on the same subject was prepared, tested and conducted. The number of surveyed farms was 345. Of them, 4,5% cooperatives, 15,5% - business companies, the rest – individual, family or group. Small was 47%, middle size – 43%, large – 10%. Again, farms were selected by type and size to represent an accurate picture of Bulgarian agriculture. Collected data were tested for representativeness. Details on this survey, collected data and results from performed tests were already published (Bachev 2025).

The goal of this article is to discover, analyze and explain changes in the choice of modes for knowledge supply during the past period. The 2023-24 survey is bigger, deeper and methodologically more modern. For comparisons and analysis here are used only questions present in the same form in both surveys. The data collected in 2001 and in 2023-24 were processed through: a) comparative quantitative analysis to detect changes over the past 23 years; b) discrete structural analysis to explain the choice of transactional mode; and c) institutional analysis to discover the causes of changes that have occurred.

Agrarian knowledge transactions through time

The first step of our study is oriented to discovering the knowledge transactions of Bulgarian farmers and make time comparisons (table 1).

Table 1: Dynamics of the share of Bulgarian farms participating in knowledge transactions (percentage of farms)

Farms	2000	2024	Trend
All	65	83	Increase
By type			
Individual, family	58	74	Increase
Cooperative	75	72	Stable
Firm	67	92	Increase
By size			
Small	65	62	Stable
Medium	60	70	Increase
Big	79	88	Increase

Sources: Field studies in 1999-2000 and 2023-2024.

Obviously, external supply of knowledge dominated Bulgarian agricultural sector and this domination increases. There is no one case of decrease. The reasons for this picture and trend could be find in:

- agriculture has been high-tech back in 2000 and has become even more high-tech over the next quarter century. The need for new knowledge has grown;
- specialization processes are developing rapidly and everything outside the core of the business is being outsourced;
- internal mode of knowledge supply is ignored as not effective.

In this situation it is interesting to see where the needed knowledge come to Bulgarian farms (table 2)

Table 2: Dynamics of the sources of knowledge for Bulgarian agriculture (percentage of all farms)

Sources	2000	2024	Trend
No use external knowledge	35	17	Decrease
Informal ¹	32	4	Decrease
Cooperative	7	4	Stable
Farmers' organization	0	n.d.	
Collective action	8	n.d.	
Market (hiring man or buying knowledge) ²	18	42	Increase
Public supply	n.d.	41	Probably increase

Sources: Field studies in 1999-2000 and 2023-2024.

1. Own experience, tradition, common practices
2. Hiring a specialist with needed skills or buying information from the market

Twice more farmers, in 2024 in comparison with those in 2000, use knowledge from outside their farms and outside their close local society (unformal and cooperative sources considerably decrease) The knowledge in 2024 comes almost entirely from market or from public sector. But it does not mean that there are no problems in knowledge supply (table 3)

Table 3. Dynamics of the problems in knowledge supply(percentage of all farms)

Problems	2000	2024	Trend
No problems	33	32	Stable
Lack of supplier	16	4	Decrease
High costs for searching supplier	25	50	Increase
Lack of needed product	16	39	Increase
Bad partners' behavior ¹	30	4	Decrease
Lack of public support	82	87	Stable
No interlinked benefits ²	67	10	Decrease

Sources: Field studies in 1999-2000 and 2023-2024.

1. In negotiation, contracting, monitoring, disputes resolution
2. Supply of knowledge in combination with other transactions – both input and output

The number of farmers declare problems remain is stable, i.e. knowledge supply is still a hard task. But two tendencies are clear. Firstly, knowledge market has developing – suppliers are more, they behave properly (in market sense), and transactions are direct not interlinked. Of course, searching within a bigger market is costly (more than two time increase of the indicator High cost of searching supplier). On second place, after a long period of pre-accession and full-accession EU support programs Bulgarian farmers they are obviously used to receiving many things as public goods including knowledge (high need of public support). And all these happens in the light of the process of deepening specialization in which the needs and requirements of the farmers increase (more than twice time more farmers declare they could not find the searched knowledge).

At the end of this part of our study we tried to find factors determined the choice of knowledge supplier. Here are the data (table 4)

Table 4. Dynamics of the supplier selection factors (percentage of all farms)

Problems	2000	2024	Trend
Price ¹	28	33	Stable
Long term contract and guarantees	28	12	Decrease
Unformal institutions ²	32	16	Decrease
Interlinked benefits	44	10	Decrease
Lack of another supplier	14	1	Decrease

Sources: Field studies in 1999-2000 and 2023-2024.

1. Including free of charge
2. Trust, confidence, reputation, non-business relations

Here we can see another confirmation of the increased trust of Bulgarian farmers in the knowledge market in 2024. They rely on it to find a supplier and do not need additional guarantees (long-term contracts or interlinked transactions). Price, of course, remains a significant factor in choosing a supplier.

Institutional modernization through time

From institutional economics point of view, critical dimensions of knowledge transactions and their state are: a) asset specificity – low, b) uncertainty – high, c) frequency – low. This is because: a) transaction are rare, b) their object is completely or largely unknown ex ante, and c) the partner in the deal could be replaced easily. In such case a) contractual mode is hardly possible (How to draw down a contract if the features and elements of its' object are hardly recognizable?), b) internal (integration within a firm) mode is not needed (transactions are rare), and c) effective mode for organization of the transaction is market.

The data from our survey demonstrate that Bulgarian farmers follow this logic. The most of them use external knowledge in increasing level (65% in 2000 and 83% in 2024). Non-use of

external knowledge falls twice (from 35% to 17% in the period). Market is a main source and its significant rise (18% in 2000 up to 42% in 2024). And it is already (in 2024) modern and enough good source (four time decrease of Lack of supplier), rejecting opportunism (more than seven times decrease of Bad partners behavior), and offering pure market transactions instead of interlinked (greatly decrease of searching for interlinked benefits).

The case of public supply with agricultural knowledge is interesting. The modern economic theory does not give us a pure economic reason for public supply with knowledge (as it is in the case of defense, for example). But it recommends two useful and effective forms - Meso-institutions and Polycentric governance. These governance mechanisms are recommended in case of deep separation between macro-economic level - where formal institutions are created and micro level - where they have to be operationalized. In such separation macro level does not fully recognizes and takes into account the problems and needs of micro level. While, micro level can hardly understand and fulfill the requirements coming from macro level (Terziev 2024).

The leading scientist in Meso-institutions theory is Claude Ménard. According to him:

Meso-institutions are the set of devices and mechanisms through which specific rules (embedded in the general ones) are delineating the domain of transactions that are possible and allowed and the modalities of their enforcement. 'Mechanisms' are here understood as the procedures through which coordination and monitoring are processed, while 'devices' are the organizational modalities through which mechanisms operate. For example, a regulation is a mechanism; a regulatory agency is a device (Ménard at all 2018: 14).

A good example of meso-institution in Bulgarian agricultural sector is National Agricultural Advisory Service, an organizational modality (device) according the Ménard's definition. It provides consultations and training to farmers on national and EU agricultural policy and instruments. These services are free of charge for farmers, i.e. – public form of knowledge supply. That is why 41% of interviewed farmers declare they use it.

We owe Polycentric Governance theory to Ostrom family. First Vincent proposed it and later Elinor developed it to entire economic governance model. She has said:

By 'polycentric' I mean a system where citizens are able to organize not just one but multiple governing authorities, as well as private arrangements, at different scales (Cole and McGinnis (eds) 2015, p. 61).

The role of Polycentric Governance mechanism in Bulgarian agriculture is played by national and EU support programs. The most important in this respect are Rural Development Programs, supported by the European agricultural fund for rural development (EAFRD). For the present period (2021-2027) it has six priorities, 18 specific focus areas, and 20 broad policy measures. The first priority is in the field of fostering knowledge transfer and innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. But knowledge dissemination is in the core of other priorities also. Beneficiaries (farmers) are obliged to follow priorities, focus areas and policy measures (all of them detailed by national authorities) but are free to develop their own governance initiatives (including private arrangements). This good example of modern Polycentric Governance is the other source for public supply of agricultural knowledge.

Conclusion

Knowledge is one of the hardest resources to be transact due to low frequency and high uncertainty of such transactions. The main conclusion of this part of our survey dedicated to agrarian knowledge transaction is that during the period of the study Bulgarian agriculture is moving in a direction of normalization. Market works better and better, and modern forms of public intervention are applied.

Well-working market does not mean easy to use and cheap market. It could be happened in case of a) lack of competition (monopoly in various forms) or b) existence of visible hand directing human activities (centrally planned economy). The economists accept both situations as not normal and not desirable.

For the modern economic theory, well-working market means: a) enough number of participants, b) domination of spontaneous actions, and c) reduction of negative behavioral proceedings. The data collected from the survey demonstrate that all these have happened in Bulgarian agriculture during the past quarter of century. Today (2024), firstly – the competition is higher (four times decrease the rate of indicator Lack of supplier and fourteen times decrease in indicator Lack of another supplier). And, of course, searching costs among many available partners are rising (two times increase the number of farmers who declared High costs of searching suppliers). On the other hand, spontaneous order is more and more preferred (two and a half time is increasing the share of farmers sourcing knowledge for themselves from the market), especially in its pure form – spot transactions (four to six time decrease in answers for searching of interlinked benefit and more than two time decrease in interest in Long term contracts and guarantees). Even the continuous high level of looking for public support indicates that market prevails. And finally, participants in the market already act as real economic agents – Bad partners' behavior decreased seven and a half times, using of informal institutions – twice.

That is what we call normalization. Institutional economic theory looks at the economic agents as individuals. They are not economic men from neoclassical theory acting equally. They differ each other by their experience and skill, knowledge and mind set, and etc. One and the same transaction could be easy and cheap for one of them but hard and expensive for other. That is why we are not looking at the market as a panacea. Many other mechanisms for economic coordination exist and each farmer is free to choose the best one for him personally. Our project is still ongoing. We are in process of preparing the first publications. That is why our analyses are still more broad and not detailed. As it was mentioned above, transactions are individual by their nature. Analyses by economic and juridical type of farms, by personal characteristics of farmers, and by other personalized criteria are forthcoming.

Acknowledgment

The study has been conducted under the project "Mechanisms and Forms of Agrarian Governance in Bulgaria", Administrative Agreement No. KP-06-N56/5 of 11.11.2021.", Scientific Research Fund, Bulgaria

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